

Quality of Sheep Meat in Silvopastoral Meadows

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Sheep and goat grazing in silvopastoral areas of Evrytania
(Photo by V. Lappa)

Lamb meat quality is influenced by a number of factors, such as the breed of lamb, its diet, the conditions under which it is reared and the way the meat is processed and handled after slaughter. Lamb is generally known for its tender texture, rich flavour and nutritional value, but its quality can vary depending on these variables.

There are many studies comparing meat quality of semi-extensively reared and intensively reared sheep. In any case, sheep grazing on grassland, especially on wooded grasslands with their high degree of plant diversity, have a higher quality of meat and in particular:

- improved fatty acid profile with an increased amount of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) and especially linked linoleic acid (CLA).
- better markers of atherosclerosis (AI) and thrombogenesis (TI)
- lowest $\omega 6/\omega 3$ fatty acid index
- better indicators of the oxidative stability of fats (reduced value of malondialdehyde in ng/g.
- bright red colour (increased a^* values in the CIE method), pleasant aroma, smooth taste.

There are of course also negatives since the meat of free-range animals is usually slightly harder, while the fat of animals with high concentrations of PUFAs is more watery.

In order to achieve the above, sheep should be able to benefit from the advantages of grazing, i.e. they should be able to utilise the pasture without having to travel huge distances which stresses them with negative consequences on their energy balance and the quality of the meat which becomes tough.

In wooded pastures, sheep should be allowed to graze freely, with proper guidance from the shepherd, with sufficient water and salt points. Trees act as shade in summer and as protection from bad weather in winter.

Ideally, the grazing period should be kept as long as possible to reduce the need for concentrated feed as much as possible. In conclusion, lamb meat quality is influenced by a number of factors such as breed, age, nutrition and grazing practices. Ensuring an impeccable and sustainable animal husbandry framework can add value to the meat produced and, consequently, more profit for the farmer.

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